

Emergency Laparotomy in Dilated Cardiomyopathy: An Anaesthesiologist's Challenge: A Case Report and Review of Literature

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Abstract:

Patient with low ejection is considered a challenge to the anaesthesiologist. Dilated cardiomyopathy (DCMP) with poor ejection fraction (EF) is a constant threat to the peri-operative morbidity and mortality. Dilated cardiomyopathy is a progressive disease characterised by the enlargement of the ventricular chambers and contractile dysfunction. In this case report, we present a 55 yr old female with idiopathic dilated cardiomyopathy and low output congestive heart failure (EF \approx 10%) who underwent emergency laparotomy for gut perforation under general anaesthesia combined with neuraxial anaesthesia without any apparent complications. Combination of evidence based and customized anaesthetic management can be of help in resource constrained emergency settings.

Keywords: Congestive Heart Failure, Dilated Cardiomyopathy, Neuraxial Anaesthesia, Non-Cardiac Surgery, Emergency Surgery.

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Introduction

Dilated cardiomyopathy is characterized by contractile dysfunction of left or both ventricles of heart leading to poor ejection fraction and low cardiac output. The decrease in forward flow causes an increase in end-diastolic ventricular volume, prompting the ventricles to enlarge in an attempt to maintain cardiac output. [1]

While DCM is often idiopathic, other causes include myocarditis, familial disease, and neuromuscular disorders. [2] The primary goal in anaesthetic management is to maintain CO by preventing tachycardia and ensuring normovolemia. Avoiding an increase in afterload is essential, as it reduces forward flow.

Optimal coronary perfusion requires maintaining normal diastolic arterial pressure, preload, and avoiding tachycardia, while reducing myocardial contractility and preventing increased systemic vascular resistance (SVR). [3]

Intravenous anesthetics are vital in managing DCM. Etomidate is preferred for induction due to its minimal myocardial depression. [4]

Propofol reduces sympathetic tone and SVR and has a negligible net effect on myocardial contractility at clinical concentrations [5].

Opioids have little cardiovascular depressant action and help reduce the dosage of general anesthetics. Neuraxial anesthesia, particularly thoracic epidural anesthesia (TEA), offers benefits by reducing afterload and maintaining forward flow. It also aids in dose reduction of intra-operative inhaled anesthetics due to its analgesic effects. [6]

Intraoperative monitoring is critical and includes standard techniques, with direct arterial blood pressure monitoring to detect abrupt hemodynamic changes. [7]

Case Report

Figure 1: Chest X-Ray showing cardiomegaly

Figure 2: ECG showing left axis deviation with poor R wave progression

A 55 year old female, weighing 45 kg presented in emergency department with complaint of pain abdomen, non-passage of stool and several episodes of vomiting for 3 days. She was diagnosed with sub-acute intestinal obstruction and was scheduled for emergency laparotomy. She was a known case of type 2 diabetes mellitus since 5 years and was on oral hypoglycemic medications. She also had shortness of breath and pedal edema. She had similar episode of shortness of breath and generalised weakness 5 months ago. Further review of her records,

revealed that she was diagnosed with idiopathic dilated cardiomyopathy. She was on tab digoxin, tab metoprolol, tab ramipril, tab torsemide and tab spironolactone for the same. On examination, bilateral crepitations on auscultation were present and baseline vitals i.e. HR-120 bpm, NIBP-90/50 mm Hg and SpO₂-95% on venturi-mask (FiO₂-0.6) were recorded. ECG showed sinus tachycardia and left axis deviation with poor R wave progression. Cardiomegaly was evident in X-ray chest. 2D Echo revealed cardiomyopathy, EF \approx 10%, Grade III and IV

left ventricular diastolic dysfunction (LVDD), mild MR and moderate TR. All these parameters were suggestive of decompensated heart failure. In view of emergency nature of procedure, general anaesthesia with thoracic epidural was planned for this patient in view of her cardiac status.

After informed written high risk consent, patient was shifted to emergency operation theatre. Defibrillator and all emergency cardiac drugs were kept ready. No premedication was advised. All ASA standard monitors (ECG, BP cuff, pulse oximeter) attached and base line vitals were recorded. IV line was secured. Under all aseptic precautions, thoracic epidural catheter was placed at level T10-T11 in sitting position, right subclavian vein and right radial arterial artery were cannulated.

Preloading was done with 200 ml balanced salt solution. Nor adrenaline infusion was started at 0.03 mcg/kg/min and titrated according to IBP targeting mean BP \approx 65 mm Hg. Test dose of 2% lignocaine (3ml) followed by 10 ml of 0.25% bupivacaine was given in aliquots through epidural catheter. Preoxygenation was started with 100% oxygen for 3 minutes, followed by rapid sequence induction with titrated doses of 180 mcg i.v Fentanyl, 50 mg ketamine, 20 mg propofol and 75mg Succinylcholine. Airway was secured with 7.00 mm ID cuffed endotracheal tube, anaesthesia was maintained with oxygen and nitrous oxide [50%,50%] in sevoflurane maintaining Minimal alveolar concentration (MAC) between 0.7-0.8 and intermittent i.v inj vecuronium.

Multimodal analgesia was given with intravenous inj fentanyl, inj paracetamol and bupivacaine infusion through epidural catheter. Inj dopamine 5 mcg/kg/min infusion was also started to maintain the target mean BP. Inj lignocaine infusion at 3mg/min was administered for frequent arrhythmias i.e. VPCs (ventricular premature complexes) in the intraoperative period. Hypokalaemia (K^+ 3.2mEq/ml) was corrected with Inj KCl 20 mEq infusion over one hour. Intraoperatively, 1L of crystalloid was given and 400 ml of blood loss was replaced with 1 unit of packed cell volume and 150 ml of fresh frozen plasma. Central venous pressure (CVP) was maintained between 8-10 cm H₂O. Hourly urine output was monitored. The surgical procedure lasted for about 3 hours. In view of haemodynamic instability, extubation trial was not given and shifted to critical care unit for elective mechanical ventilation. In the post-operative period vasopressor support was gradually tapered and patient was extubated after 36 hours of surgery.

Discussion

Dilated cardiomyopathy is characterized by the contractile dysfunction of the left or both the ventricles of the heart. The failure to eject adequate amount of blood may lead to the poor ejection fraction (EF) and low cardiac output (CO). There will be increase in

the end diastolic ventricular volume due to the decrease in the forward flow which leads to the enlargement of the ventricles to maintain the CO. Mostly, DCM is idiopathic in origin. There may be other causes also such as myocarditis, familial disease, neuromuscular disorders [2]. The preoperative preparation of such patient is very important.

Goal of the anaesthetic management in such patient is maintenance of CO which is achieved by preventing tachycardia and maintaining normovolemia. Increase in afterload is avoided as it results in decrease in forward flow. R.J. Ing et al. investigated anaesthetic management in pediatric cardiomyopathy cases, recommended that to optimize coronary perfusion, normal diastolic arterial pressure should be maintained. They also emphasized the importance of maintaining preload, avoiding tachycardia, reducing myocardial contractility, and preventing increased systemic vascular resistance (SVR) as key anaesthetic principles for managing dilated cardiomyopathy (DCM). [3]

Intravenous Anaesthetics

Chen CQ et al. proposed Etomidate as preferred induction agent for preventing myocardial depression. Effect of ketamine was studied by Raj R et al. They observed that because of sympathetic stimulation action, Ketamine increases after load, thus avoided for induction. But in patients with severe dysfunction of myocardium, induction can be done with ketamine along with propofol, midazolam or opioids like fentanyl [8]. Propofol role in reduction in sympathetic tone and systemic vascular resistance was studied by Yamaguchi S et al. [5]. Riou B et al. Studied that propofol also has some direct negative inotropic effect on heart but studies have shown that net effect on myocardial contractility is insignificant in clinically used concentrations [9]. Opioid role in dose reduction of general anaesthetics for both induction as well as maintenance was studied by Raj R et al. They observed that opioids have little or no cardiovascular depressant action. High concentration of volatile anaesthetic agents should be avoided because of their myocardial depressant action [8]. So, alveolar concentration of the inhaled anaesthetic should be maintained low according to the MAC and BIS monitoring [4].

Neuraxial Anaesthesia

Chen CQ et al. study proposed benefits of neuraxial blockade in reducing the afterload and maintaining the forward flow of the blood. Sympathetic stimulation should be avoided to prevent tachycardia and maintaining the forward flow [8]. Similarly, research by K Kirno et al., studied the effect of thoracic epidural anaesthesia (TEA) on cardiac sympathetic activity, myocardial central hemodynamics and myocardial blood flow and metabolism. They found that TEA reduces the sympathetic stress re-

sponse to sternotomy, thus preventing increased myocardial oxygen demand before bypass period without compromising myocardial perfusion [10].

Role of TEA in normalizing blood flow of myocardium in response to sympathetic stimulation in patients with multi-vessel ischemic heart disease was reported by Eigil Nygad et al [11]. Ma D et al. concluded that sympathetic blockade seen with thoracic epidural increases blood flow of myocardium and can reverse myocardial fibrosis and improve cardiac function in patients with heart failure caused by DCM [12]. Epidural anaesthesia association with dose reduction of the intra-operative inhaled anaesthetics because of analgesic action was studied by Shaheen MS et al. [6]. Large dose of local anesthesia may cause a reduction in SVR and impairment of myocardial function. To avoid rapid and extensive sympathetic nerve block, slow titration or administration of low-dose of local anesthesia was recommended by George L M et al. [13]

Intraoperative Monitoring

In addition to the basic monitoring (BP, pulse oximeter, EKG, end-tidal CO₂) Thiagarajah PH et al. recommended monitoring of direct arterial blood pressure to identify abrupt hemodynamic changes [7]. Importance of transesophageal echocardiography (TEE) monitoring in complex or long duration surgeries was studied by Udelson I et al. [14]. TEE helps to identify the cause of hypotension during anaesthetic management by differentiating between global hypokinesia, hypovolemia and regional ischemic ventricular dysfunction. Recently, intraoperative Doppler tissue imaging (DTI) has been added as a valuable diagnostic tool [15].

Daniel I. Sessler et al. found that the occurrence of low mean arterial pressure (MAP) during low minimum alveolar concentration (MAC) fractions was a strong and highly significantly predicted increased mortality. The risk of mortality was further elevated when these conditions were combined with low bispectral index (BIS). For cardiac surgery patients, maintaining a pulmonary artery wedge pressure of 12-15 mmHg or a central venous pressure (CVP) of 8-12 mmHg is recommended. [16].

In our case, invasive blood pressure monitoring was utilized for the early detection and treatment of hypotension and central venous pressure monitoring was employed to optimize fluid therapy. However, BIS and transesophageal echocardiography (TEE) monitoring were not done due to their non-availability in the emergency setting.

Vasoactive Drugs

Maekawa T. studied the anesthetic management in patients with dilated cardiomyopathy who are undergoing non-cardiac surgery and concluded that in-

otropic support, catecholamines or phosphodiesterase inhibitors with or without vasodilators prevent perioperative low cardiac output syndrome [17].

According to recommendations by Mebazaa A et al., catecholamines like Dobutamine and epinephrine, when used in low-to-moderate doses, can improve stroke volume and heart rate while moderately reducing PCWP. However, they also increase oxygen consumption of myocardium. Milrinone is noted to decrease PCWP and SVR, increase stroke volume and causes less tachycardia compared to dobutamine. Levosimendan, a calcium sensitizer, also increases stroke volume and heart rate while reducing SVR. In cases of low blood pressure due to vasoplegia, norepinephrine is recommended to maintain an adequate perfusion pressure. Additionally, hypovolaemia should be frequently ruled out while using vasopressors. [18]

Smaller combined doses of inotropes and vasopressors are advantageous over a single agent used at higher doses to avoid dose-related adverse effects. In cardiogenic shock complicating AMI, current guidelines based on expert opinion recommend dopamine or dobutamine as first-line agents with moderate hypotension (systolic blood pressure 70 to 100 mm Hg) and norepinephrine as the preferred therapy for severe hypotension (systolic blood pressure <70 mm Hg) [19]. Chen CQ recommended use of low dose infusion of dopamine before induction of anesthesia to prevent hypotension during induction [4]. In the post-operative period, a cardiologist opinion should be recommended.

Conclusion

Anaesthetic management in DCMP patients with low ejection fraction is really challenging to the anesthesiologist. Combination of epidural anesthesia with general anesthesia is preferred in patient of DCM posted for emergency laprotomy. Epidural anaesthesia reduces the afterload, improves the cardiac output and decreases the drug dosage of the inhaled anaesthetics in the intra-operative period.

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